

Crop management

Influence of planting dates on productivity of traditional scented rice varieties

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To exploit the full yield potential of traditional scented rice varieties, it is necessary to determine their optimum planting time for specific locations. A field experiment was conducted during the 1993 and 1994 wet seasons using a split-plot design with four dates of planting as main plot treatments and three varieties of traditional Basmati as subplot treatments, replicated four times.

Soil at the experimental site was sandy loam, low in organic C (0.41%), low in available P (7.7 kg ha⁻¹), and medium in K (178.5 kg ha⁻¹) with pH 7.8. The crop was fertilized with 60, 13.2, and 24.9 kg of N, P, and K ha⁻¹, respectively of which 50% N, full P, and K along with 5.8 kg Zn ha⁻¹ were applied uniformly as basal dressing and incorporated. The other 50% N was applied in two equal splits at tillering and panicle initiation. Seedlings (21 d old) were transplanted at 20- × 15-cm spacing with 2-3 seedlings hill⁻¹.

Dates of planting influenced the grain yield of Basmati rice significantly during both years of study (see table). The highest mean grain yield was recorded from the 1 Jul planting date and did not differ significantly from the 16 Jul planting, but yield differed from that of 31 Jul and 16 Aug. A linear reduction in grain yield with every 15-d delay in planting was recorded from 1 Jul (4.1 t ha⁻¹) to 16 Aug (2.5 t ha⁻¹). The percent reduction in grain yield averaged over 2 yr was 11.8, 20.8, and 37.4%, respectively, for 16 Jul, 31 Jul, and 16 Aug as compared with the grain yield of the 1 Jul planting. In yield-contributing characters, panicle weight differed significantly during both years while panicles m⁻² differed only during

1994. The maximum panicles m⁻² were recorded for the 1 Jul planting, whereas panicle weight remained the same for the 1 Jul and 16 Jul plantings. The interaction between planting dates × varieties was not significant.

The test varieties did not differ significantly among themselves in grain yield. Basmati 370 had a slightly higher grain yield (3.40 t ha⁻¹), followed by Taraori Basmati (3.38 t ha⁻¹). Basmati 370 also had the highest average

panicles m⁻² (387 m⁻²) while Taraori Basmati had the highest average panicle weight (1.67 g panicle⁻¹).

Results indicated that Basmati 370 could be used for early planting whereas Ranveer Basmati could be used for delayed planting. The higher grain yield of such traditional scented rice varieties could be achieved by transplanting them during the first fortnight of July in the western part of Uttar Pradesh. ■

Grain yield and yield-contributing characters of traditional scented rice varieties under different planting dates. Uttar Pradesh, India, 1993-94 wet seasons.

Treatment	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)			Panicles m ⁻² (no.)			Panicle weight(g)		
	1993	1994	Mean	1993	1994	Mean	1993	1994	Mean
<i>Planting date</i>									
1 Jul	4.2	3.9	4.1	406	358	382	1.74	1.68	1.71
16 Jul	3.6	3.5	3.6	369	345	357	1.71	1.70	1.71
31 Jul	3.3	3.1	3.2	385	330	358	1.67	1.59	1.63
16 Aug	2.8	2.3	2.5	378	309	344	1.62	1.55	1.59
CD (5%)	0.9	0.7	-	ns	15	-	0.03	0.05	-
<i>Variety</i>									
Basmati 370	3.5	3.3	3.4	409	365	387	1.64	1.60	1.62
Ranveer Basmati	3.5	3.1	3.3	383	355	369	1.67	1.52	1.60
Taraori Basmati	3.5	3.2	3.4	361	360	361	1.73	1.61	1.67
CD (5%)	ns	ns	-	ns	9	-	0.02	0.06	0

Seedling vigor affects stand establishment and performance of flood-prone lowland rice

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We conducted a field experiment at Cuttack, India, during 1993 using three long-duration, photoperiod-sensitive rice varieties of different plant heights. Vegetative tillers were transplanted from conventional nursery seedbeds unfertilized or with N fertilization (100 kg N ha⁻¹ at sowing). Their performance was compared with that of sowings at 400 kg N ha⁻¹ in a nursery seedbed in a relatively upland field and 80 kg N ha⁻¹ in a lowland field, from where about 100 tillers m⁻² were up-

rooted and transplanted. Seedlings and vegetative tillers (45 d old) were transplanted into 8 cm of water at 20- × 15-cm spacing of 2-3 hill⁻¹ in a randomized block design with three replications and fertilized with a basal dose of 40 kg N ha⁻¹, 8.7 kg P ha⁻¹, and 16.7 kg K ha⁻¹.

Vigor depended on variety and type of seedling (see table). Fertilizer N application in the seedbed improved height and dry weight compared with unfertilized seedlings.

Two floods occurred within the month of transplanting (see figure). The taller and heavier plants were well established when subjected to 54 cm of water 4 d after transplanting. Plants raised from nursery seedlings suffered the greatest damage. Unfertilized seed-